

Representation of Graph Structure Based on I-V Neutrosophic Sets

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Abstract. In this research article, we apply the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic sets to graph structures. We present the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic graph structures. We describe certain operations on interval-valued neutrosophic graph structures and elaborate them with appropriate examples. Further, we investigate some relevant properties of these operators. Moreover, we propose some open problems on interval-valued neutrosophic line graph structures.

1. Introduction

Zadeh [26] proposed fuzzy set theory to deal with uncertainty in many meticulous real-life phenomena. Fuzzy set theory is affluently applicable in real time systems having information with different levels of precision. Zadeh introduced interval-valued fuzzy sets as generalization of fuzzy sets in [27]. There are many natural phenomena, in which with membership value it is necessary to consider non-membership value. Membership value of an event is in its favor, whereas non-membership value is in its opposition. Atanassov [10] introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets as an extension of fuzzy sets. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets are more practical, advantageous and applicable in many real-life phenomena. In many real-life phenomena like information fusion, indeterminacy is doubtlessly quantified. Smarandache [19, 20] proposed the notion of neutrosophic sets, he combined non-standard analysis, tricomponent logic, and philosophy. "It is a branch of philosophy which studies the origin, nature and scope of neutralities as well as their interactions with different ideational spectra". In neutrosophic set, three independent components are: truth-membership (t), indeterminacy-membership (i) and falsity-membership (f), each membership value is a real standard or non-standard subset of the non-standard unit interval $]0^-, 1^+[$ and there is no restriction on their sum. For convenient and advantageous use of neutrosophic sets in science and engineering, Wang et al. [22] introduced the idea of single-valued neutrosophic(SVN) sets, whose three independent components t , i and f have values in standard unit interval $[0, 1]$ and their sum does not exceed three. Neutrosophic set theory is a generalization of the fuzzy set theory and intuitionistic fuzzy set theory. It is more advantageous and applicable in many fields, including medical diagnosis, control theory, topology, decision making problems and in many more real-life problems. Wang et al. [23] presented the notion of interval-valued neutrosophic sets, it is more precise and more flexible as compared to single-valued neutrosophic set. An interval-valued neutrosophic set is a generalization of the concept of single-valued neutrosophic set, in which values of three independent components (t, i, f) are intervals, which are subsets

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of standard unit interval $[0, 1]$.

On the basis of Zadeh's fuzzy relations [28], Kaufmann proposed fuzzy graph [15]. Rosenfeld [17] discussed fuzzy analogue of various graph-theoretic ideas. Later on, Bhattacharya [11] gave some remarks on fuzzy graphs, and some operations on fuzzy graphs were introduced by Mordeson and Peng [16]. The complement of a fuzzy graph was defined by Mordeson [16] and further studied by Sunitha and Vijayakumar [21]. Hongmei and Lianhua gave the definition of interval-valued fuzzy graph in [14]. After that, Akram et al. [1-4] considered several concepts on interval-valued fuzzy graphs. Recently, Akram and Nasir [5] dealt with interval-valued neutrosophic graphs. Akram and Shahzadi [6] introduced the notion of neutrosophic soft graphs with applications. Akram [7] introduced the notion of single-valued neutrosophic planar graphs. Dinesh and Ramakrishnan [13] defined fuzzy graph structures and discussed its properties. Akram and Akmal [9] proposed the notion of bipolar fuzzy graph structures. In this research article, we first present the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic line graphs as an extension of interval-valued fuzzy line graphs [1]. We then present concept of interval-valued neutrosophic graph structures. Further, we describe certain operations on interval-valued neutrosophic graph structures. Finally, we state some open problems on interval-valued neutrosophic line graph structures.

2. Background

Wang et al. [23] introduced the concept of interval-valued (I-V) neutrosophic sets as follows:

Definition 2.1. [23, 24] *The interval-valued neutrosophic set A in X is defined by*

$$A = \{(x, [t_A^-(x), t_A^+(x)], [i_A^-(x), i_A^+(x)], [f_A^-(x), f_A^+(x)]) : x \in X\},$$

where, $t_A^-(x)$, $t_A^+(x)$, $i_A^-(x)$, $i_A^+(x)$, $f_A^-(x)$, and $f_A^+(x)$ are neutrosophic subsets of X such that $t_A^-(x) \leq t_A^+(x)$, $i_A^-(x) \leq i_A^+(x)$ and $f_A^-(x) \leq f_A^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

For any two interval-valued neutrosophic sets $A = ([t_A^-(x), t_A^+(x)], [i_A^-(x), i_A^+(x)], [f_A^-(x), f_A^+(x)])$ and $B = ([t_B^-(x), t_B^+(x)], [i_B^-(x), i_B^+(x)], [f_B^-(x), f_B^+(x)])$ in X , we define:

- $A \cup B = \{(x, \max(t_A^-(x), t_B^-(x)), \max(t_A^+(x), t_B^+(x)), \max(i_A^-(x), i_B^-(x)), \max(i_A^+(x), i_B^+(x)), \min(f_A^-(x), f_B^-(x)), \min(f_A^+(x), f_B^+(x))) : x \in X\}$.
- $A \cap B = \{(x, \min(t_A^-(x), t_B^-(x)), \min(t_A^+(x), t_B^+(x)), \min(i_A^-(x), i_B^-(x)), \min(i_A^+(x), i_B^+(x)), \max(f_A^-(x), f_B^-(x)), \max(f_A^+(x), f_B^+(x))) : x \in X\}$.

Akram and Nasir [5] defined interval-valued neutrosophic graph as follows:

Definition 2.2. [5] *An interval-valued neutrosophic graph on a nonempty set X is a pair $G = (A, B)$, where A is an interval-valued neutrosophic set on X and B is an interval-valued neutrosophic relation on X such that:*

1. $t_B^-(xy) \leq \min(t_A^-(x), t_A^-(y)),$ $t_B^+(xy) \leq \min(t_A^+(x), t_A^+(y)),$
2. $i_B^-(xy) \leq \min(i_A^-(x), i_A^-(y)),$ $i_B^+(xy) \leq \min(i_A^+(x), i_A^+(y)),$
3. $f_B^-(xy) \leq \min(f_A^-(x), f_A^-(y)),$ $f_B^+(xy) \leq \min(f_A^+(x), f_A^+(y)),$

for all $x, y \in X$. Note that B is called symmetric relation on A .

We now introduce the notion of an interval-valued neutrosophic line graph as a generalization of an interval-valued fuzzy line graph [1].

Definition 2.3. *Let $L(\hat{G}) = (X, Y)$ be line graph of the crisp graph $\hat{G} = (V, E)$. Let $A_1 = ([t_{A_1}^-, t_{A_1}^+], [i_{A_1}^-, i_{A_1}^+], [f_{A_1}^-, f_{A_1}^+])$ and $B_1 = ([t_{B_1}^-, t_{B_1}^+], [i_{B_1}^-, i_{B_1}^+], [f_{B_1}^-, f_{B_1}^+])$ be interval-valued neutrosophic sets on V and E , $A_2 = ([t_{A_2}^-, t_{A_2}^+], [i_{A_2}^-, i_{A_2}^+], [f_{A_2}^-, f_{A_2}^+])$ and $B_2 = ([t_{B_2}^-, t_{B_2}^+], [i_{B_2}^-, i_{B_2}^+], [f_{B_2}^-, f_{B_2}^+])$ on X and Y , respectively. Then an interval-valued neutrosophic line graph of the interval-valued neutrosophic graph $G = (A_1, B_1)$ is an interval-valued neutrosophic graph $L(G) = (A_2, B_2)$ such that*

- (i) $t_{A_2}^-(S_x) = t_{B_1}^-(x) = t_{B_1}^-(u_x v_x)$, $t_{A_2}^+(S_x) = t_{B_1}^+(x) = t_{B_1}^+(u_x v_x)$,
- (ii) $i_{A_2}^-(S_x) = i_{B_1}^-(x) = i_{B_1}^-(u_x v_x)$, $i_{A_2}^+(S_x) = i_{B_1}^+(x) = i_{B_1}^+(u_x v_x)$,
- (iii) $f_{A_2}^-(S_x) = f_{B_1}^-(x) = f_{B_1}^-(u_x v_x)$, $f_{A_2}^+(S_x) = f_{B_1}^+(x) = f_{B_1}^+(u_x v_x)$,
- (iv) $t_{B_2}^-(S_x S_y) = \min(t_{B_1}^-(x), t_{B_1}^-(y))$, $t_{B_2}^+(S_x S_y) = \min(t_{B_1}^+(x), t_{B_1}^+(y))$,
- (v) $i_{B_2}^-(S_x S_y) = \min(i_{B_1}^-(x), i_{B_1}^-(y))$, $i_{B_2}^+(S_x S_y) = \min(i_{B_1}^+(x), i_{B_1}^+(y))$,
- (vi) $f_{B_2}^-(S_x S_y) = \min(f_{B_1}^-(x), f_{B_1}^-(y))$, $f_{B_2}^+(S_x S_y) = \min(f_{B_1}^+(x), f_{B_1}^+(y))$,

for all $S_x, S_y \in X$, $S_x S_y \in Y$.

Proposition 2.4. $L(G) = (A_2, B_2)$ is an interval-valued neutrosophic line graph of some interval-valued neutrosophic graph $G = (A_1, B_1)$ if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} t_{B_2}^-(S_x S_y) &= \min(t_{A_2}^-(S_x), t_{A_2}^-(S_y)), & t_{B_2}^+(S_x S_y) &= \min(t_{A_2}^+(S_x), t_{A_2}^+(S_y)), \\ i_{B_2}^-(S_x S_y) &= \min(i_{A_2}^-(S_x), i_{A_2}^-(S_y)), & i_{B_2}^+(S_x S_y) &= \min(i_{A_2}^+(S_x), i_{A_2}^+(S_y)), \\ f_{B_2}^-(S_x S_y) &= \min(f_{A_2}^-(S_x), f_{A_2}^-(S_y)), & f_{B_2}^+(S_x S_y) &= \min(f_{A_2}^+(S_x), f_{A_2}^+(S_y)), \end{aligned}$$

$\forall S_x, S_y \in Y$.

Proof. By using similar arguments as used in the proof of Proposition 3.7 of [1], the proof is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 2.5. Consider two interval-valued neutrosophic graphs $G_1 = (A_1, B_1)$ and $G_2 = (A_2, B_2)$. A mapping $\varphi : V_1 \rightarrow V_2$ is called homomorphism $\varphi : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ if

$$\begin{aligned} (a) \quad & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_{A_1}^-(x_1) \leq t_{A_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)), \quad i_{A_1}^-(x_1) \leq i_{A_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)), \quad f_{A_1}^-(x_1) \leq f_{A_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)), \\ t_{A_1}^+(x_1) \leq t_{A_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)), \quad i_{A_1}^+(x_1) \leq i_{A_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)), \quad f_{A_1}^+(x_1) \leq f_{A_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)), \end{array} \right. \\ (b) \quad & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1) \leq t_{B_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \quad t_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1) \leq t_{B_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \\ i_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1) \leq i_{B_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \quad i_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1) \leq i_{B_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \\ f_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1) \leq f_{B_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \quad f_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1) \leq f_{B_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \end{array} \right. \end{aligned}$$

for all $x_1 \in V_1$, $x_1 y_1 \in E_1$. Weak vertex-isomorphism of interval-valued neutrosophic graphs is a bijective homomorphism $\varphi : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$, such that

$$(c) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_{A_1}^-(x_1) = t_{A_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)), \quad i_{A_1}^-(x_1) = i_{A_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)), \quad f_{A_1}^-(x_1) = f_{A_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)), \\ t_{A_1}^+(x_1) = t_{A_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)), \quad i_{A_1}^+(x_1) = i_{A_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)), \quad f_{A_1}^+(x_1) = f_{A_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)), \end{array} \right.$$

for all $x_1 \in V_1$ and $\varphi : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ is called weak line-isomorphism if

$$(d) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1) = t_{B_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \quad t_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1) = t_{B_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \\ i_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1) = i_{B_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \quad i_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1) = i_{B_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \\ f_{B_1}^-(x_1 y_1) = f_{B_2}^-(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \quad f_{B_1}^+(x_1 y_1) = f_{B_2}^+(\varphi(x_1)\varphi(y_1)), \end{array} \right.$$

for all $x_1 y_1 \in V_1$. Weak isomorphism $\varphi : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ of two interval-valued neutrosophic graphs G_1 and G_2 is bijective homomorphism and satisfies (c) and (d). Weak isomorphism may not preserve the weights of the edges but preserves the weights of vertices.

Theorem 2.6. Let $L(G) = (A_2, B_2)$ be an interval-valued neutrosophic line graph corresponding to an interval-valued neutrosophic graph $G = (A_1, B_1)$. Suppose that $\hat{G} = (V, E)$ is a connected graph. Then

(i) there is a weak isomorphism between G and $L(G)$ if and only if $\hat{G}$ is a cyclic graph and $\forall v \in V, x \in E,$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{A_1}^-(v) &= t_{B_1}^-(x), i_{A_1}^-(v) = i_{B_1}^-(x), f_{A_1}^-(v) = f_{B_1}^-(x), \\ t_{A_1}^+(v) &= t_{B_1}^+(x), i_{A_1}^+(v) = i_{B_1}^+(x), f_{A_1}^+(v) = f_{B_1}^+(x), \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $A_1 = ([t_{A_1}^-, t_{A_1}^+], [i_{A_1}^-, i_{A_1}^+], [f_{A_1}^-, f_{A_1}^+])$ and $B_1 = ([t_{B_1}^-, t_{B_1}^+], [i_{B_1}^-, i_{B_1}^+], [f_{B_1}^-, f_{B_1}^+])$ are constant functions on the sets V and E , respectively, taking on same value.

(ii) If φ is a weak isomorphism between G and $L(G)$, then φ is an isomorphism.

Proof. By using similar arguments as used in the proof of Theorem 3.11 of [1], the proof is straightforward. $\square$

3. Operations on I-V Neutrosophic Graph Structures

In this section, we describe certain methods of construction of new interval-valued neutrosophic graph structures from old one.

Definition 3.1. $\check{G}_{iv} = (I, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_t)$ is called an interval-valued neutrosophic graph structure (IVNGS) of graph structure $G_s = (U, U_1, U_2, \dots, U_t)$ if $I = \langle r, [t^-(r), t^+(r)], [i^-(r), i^+(r)], [f^-(r), f^+(r)] \rangle$ and $I_j = \langle rs, [t^-(rs), t^+(rs)], [i^-(rs), i^+(rs)], [f^-(rs), f^+(rs)] \rangle$ are interval-valued neutrosophic (IVN) sets on U and U_j , respectively, such that:

1. $t_j^-(rs) \leq \min\{t^-(r), t^-(s)\}, \quad t_j^+(rs) \leq \min\{t^+(r), t^+(s)\},$
2. $i_j^-(rs) \leq \min\{i^-(r), i^-(s)\}, \quad i_j^+(rs) \leq \min\{i^+(r), i^+(s)\},$
3. $f_j^-(rs) \leq \min\{f^-(r), f^-(s)\}, \quad f_j^+(rs) \leq \min\{f^+(r), f^+(s)\},$

for all $r, s \in U$. Note that $0 \leq t_j(rs) + i_j(rs) + f_j(rs) \leq 3$, for all $(rs) \in U_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, t$.

Example 3.2. Consider graph structure $G_s = (U, U_1, U_2)$ such that $U = \{r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4, r_5, r_6\}, U_1 = \{r_1r_4, r_2r_4, r_2r_6\}, U_2 = \{r_1r_5, r_3r_5, r_3r_6\}$. Let I be an IVN set on U given in Table. 1 and I_1, I_2 be IVN sets on U_1, U_2 , respectively given in Table. 2. and Table. 3.

Table 1: IVN set I on vertex set U

I	r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6
t^-	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3
t^+	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.4
i^-	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.1
i^+	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.2
f^-	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.3
f^+	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.4

Table 2: IVN set I_1 on set U_1

I_1	r_1r_4	r_2r_4	r_2r_6
t^-	0.1	0.1	0.3
t^+	0.2	0.2	0.4
i^-	0.3	0.4	0.1
i^+	0.4	0.5	0.2
f^-	0.2	0.2	0.3
f^+	0.3	0.3	0.4

Table 3: IVN set I_2 on set U_2

I_2	r_1r_5	r_3r_5	r_3r_6
t^-	0.2	0.3	0.3
t^+	0.3	0.4	0.4
i^-	0.3	0.4	0.1
i^+	0.4	0.5	0.2
f^-	0.3	0.3	0.3
f^+	0.4	0.4	0.4

Routine calculations show that $\check{G}_{iv} = (I, I_1, I_2)$ is an interval-valued neutrosophic graph structure, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: An IVNGS $\check{G}_{iv} = (I, I_1, I_2)$

We now present some operations on IVNGSs.

Definition 3.3. Let $\check{G}_{iv1} = (I_1, I_{11}, I_{12}, \dots, I_{1t})$ and $\check{G}_{iv2} = (I_2, I_{21}, I_{22}, \dots, I_{2t})$ be two IVNGSs of graph structures $G_{s1} = (U_1, U_{11}, U_{12}, \dots, U_{1t})$ and $G_{s2} = (U_2, U_{21}, U_{22}, \dots, U_{2t})$, respectively. Cartesian product of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$, denoted by

$$\check{G}_{iv1} \times \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \times I_2, I_{11} \times I_{21}, I_{12} \times I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \times I_{2t}),$$

is defined as:

$$(i) \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^-(rs) = (t_{I_1}^- \times t_{I_2}^-)(rs) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^-(rs) = (i_{I_1}^- \times i_{I_2}^-)(rs) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^-(rs) = (f_{I_1}^- \times f_{I_2}^-)(rs) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s) \end{cases}$$

$$(ii) \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^+(rs) = (t_{I_1}^+ \times t_{I_2}^+)(rs) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^+(rs) = (i_{I_1}^+ \times i_{I_2}^+)(rs) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^+(rs) = (f_{I_1}^+ \times f_{I_2}^+)(rs) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s) \end{cases}$$

for all $rs \in U_1 \times U_2$,

$$(iii) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \times t_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \times i_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \times f_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \end{cases}$$

$$(iv) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \times t_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \times i_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \times f_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \end{cases}$$

for all $r \in U_1, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$,

$$(v) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^-(r_1s)(r_2s) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \times t_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s)(r_2s) = t_{I_{2j}}^-(s) \wedge t_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^-(r_1s)(r_2s) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \times i_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s)(r_2s) = i_{I_{2j}}^-(s) \wedge i_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \times I_{2j})}^-(r_1s)(r_2s) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \times f_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s)(r_2s) = f_{I_{2j}}^-(s) \wedge f_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \end{cases}$$

$$(vi) \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^+(r_1s)(r_2s) = (t_{I_1}^+ \times t_{I_2}^+)(r_1s)(r_2s) = t_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(r_1r_2) \\ i_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^+(r_1s)(r_2s) = (i_{I_1}^+ \times i_{I_2}^+)(r_1s)(r_2s) = i_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(r_1r_2) \\ f_{(I_1 \times I_2)}^+(r_1s)(r_2s) = (f_{I_1}^+ \times f_{I_2}^+)(r_1s)(r_2s) = f_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(r_1r_2) \end{cases}$$

for all $s \in U_2, r_1r_2 \in U_{1j}, j = 1, 2, \dots, t$.

Example 3.4. Consider $\check{G}_{iv1} = (I_1, I_{11}, I_{12})$ and $\check{G}_{iv2} = (I_2, I_{21}, I_{22})$ are two IVNGSSs of graph structures $\check{G}_{s1} = (U_1, U_{11}, U_{12})$ and $\check{G}_{s2} = (U_2, U_{21}, U_{22})$, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2, where $U_{11} = \{r_1r_2\}$, $U_{12} = \{r_3r_4\}$, $U_{21} = \{s_1s_2\}$, $U_{22} = \{s_2s_3\}$.

Figure 2: Two IVNGSSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$

Cartesian product of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ defined as $\check{G}_{iv1} \times \check{G}_{iv2} = \{I_1 \times I_2, I_{11} \times I_{21}, I_{12} \times I_{22}\}$ is shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(iii)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 * I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (t_{I_1}^- * t_{I_2}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = t_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ i_{(I_1 * I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (i_{I_1}^- * i_{I_2}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = i_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ f_{(I_1 * I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (f_{I_1}^- * f_{I_2}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = f_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(iv)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 * I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (t_{I_1}^+ * t_{I_2}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = t_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ i_{(I_1 * I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (i_{I_1}^+ * i_{I_2}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = i_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ f_{(I_1 * I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (f_{I_1}^+ * f_{I_2}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = f_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \end{cases} \\
 & \text{for all } r_1 r_2 \in U_{1j}, s_1 s_2 \in U_{2j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.7. Cross product of IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ shown in Fig. 2 is defined as $\check{G}_{iv1} * \check{G}_{iv2} = \{I_1 * I_2, I_{11} * I_{21}, I_{12} * I_{22}\}$ and is shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

Figure 5: $\check{G}_{iv1} * \check{G}_{iv2}$

Figure 6: $\check{G}_{iv1} * \check{G}_{iv2}$

Theorem 3.8. Cross product $\check{G}_{iv1} * \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 * I_2, I_{11} * I_{21}, I_{12} * I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} * I_{2t})$ of two IVNGSs of graph structures G_{s1} and G_{s2} is an IVNGS of $G_{s1} * G_{s2}$.

Definition 3.9. Let $\check{G}_{iv1} = (I_1, I_{11}, I_{12}, \dots, I_{1t})$ and $\check{G}_{iv2} = (I_2, I_{21}, I_{22}, \dots, I_{2t})$ be two IVNGSs. Lexicographic product of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$, denoted by

$$\check{G}_{iv1} \bullet \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \bullet I_2, I_{11} \bullet I_{21}, I_{12} \bullet I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \bullet I_{2t}),$$

is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(i)} & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-(rs) = (t_{I_1}^- \bullet t_{I_2}^-)(rs) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-(rs) = (i_{I_1}^- \bullet i_{I_2}^-)(rs) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-(rs) = (f_{I_1}^- \bullet f_{I_2}^-)(rs) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(ii)} & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+(rs) = (t_{I_1}^+ \bullet t_{I_2}^+)(rs) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+(rs) = (i_{I_1}^+ \bullet i_{I_2}^+)(rs) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+(rs) = (f_{I_1}^+ \bullet f_{I_2}^+)(rs) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s) \end{cases} \\
 & \text{for all } rs \in U_1 \times U_2, \\
 \text{(iii)} & \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \bullet t_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \bullet i_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \bullet f_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(iv)} & \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \bullet t_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \bullet i_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \bullet f_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \end{cases} \\
 & \text{for all } r \in U_1, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}, \\
 \text{(v)} & \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^-(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \bullet t_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^-(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \bullet i_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge i_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^-(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \bullet f_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^-(s_1s_2) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(vi)} & \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^+(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \bullet t_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^+(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \bullet i_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge i_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \bullet I_{2j})}^+(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \bullet f_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \end{cases} \\
 & \text{for all } r_1r_2 \in U_{1j}, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.10. Lexicographic product of IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ shown in Fig. 2 is defined as $\check{G}_{iv1} \bullet \check{G}_{iv2} = \{I_1 \bullet I_2, I_{11} \bullet I_{21}, I_{12} \bullet I_{22}\}$ and is depicted in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Figure 7: $\check{G}_{iv1} \bullet \check{G}_{iv2}$

Figure 8: $\check{G}_{iv1} \bullet \check{G}_{iv2}$

Theorem 3.11. Lexicographic product $\check{G}_{iv1} \bullet \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \bullet I_2, I_{11} \bullet I_{21}, I_{12} \bullet I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \bullet I_{2t})$ of two IVNGSs of graph structures G_{s_1} and G_{s_2} is an IVNGS of $G_{s_1} \bullet G_{s_2}$.

Proof. Consider two cases:

Case 1. For $r \in U_1, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$,

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge t_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \bullet I_2)}^+(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

for $rs_1, rs_2 \in U_1 \bullet U_2$.

Case 2. For $r_1r_2 \in U_{1j}, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$,

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-((r_1s_1)(r_2s_2)) &= t_{I_1}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq [t_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(r_1s_1) \wedge t_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(r_2s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+((r_1s_1)(r_2s_2)) &= t_{I_1}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq [t_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(r_1s_1) \wedge t_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(r_2s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-((r_1s_1)(r_2s_2)) &= i_{I_1}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq [i_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(r_1s_1) \wedge i_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(r_2s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+((r_1s_1)(r_2s_2)) &= i_{I_1}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq [i_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(r_1s_1) \wedge i_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(r_2s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-((r_1s_1)(r_2s_2)) &= f_{I_1}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq [f_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [f_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(r_1s_1) \wedge f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^-(r_2s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{(I_{1j}, \bullet I_{2j})}^+((r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2)) &= f_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1 s_2) \\
 &\leq [f_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
 &= [f_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
 &= f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1) \wedge f_{(I_1, \bullet I_2)}^+(r_2 s_2),
 \end{aligned}$$

$r_1 s_1, r_2 s_2 \in U_1 \bullet U_2$ and $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$. This completes the proof.

□

Definition 3.12. Let $\check{G}_{iv1} = (I_1, I_{11}, I_{12}, \dots, I_{1t})$ and $\check{G}_{iv2} = (I_2, I_{21}, I_{22}, \dots, I_{2t})$ be two IVNGSs. Strong product of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$, denoted by

$$\check{G}_{iv1} \boxtimes \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \boxtimes I_2, I_{11} \boxtimes I_{21}, I_{12} \boxtimes I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \boxtimes I_{2t}),$$

is defined as:

- (i) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs) = (t_{I_1}^- \boxtimes t_{I_2}^-)(rs) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs) = (i_{I_1}^- \boxtimes i_{I_2}^-)(rs) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs) = (f_{I_1}^- \boxtimes f_{I_2}^-)(rs) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s) \end{cases}$
- (ii) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs) = (t_{I_1}^+ \boxtimes t_{I_2}^+)(rs) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs) = (i_{I_1}^+ \boxtimes i_{I_2}^+)(rs) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs) = (f_{I_1}^+ \boxtimes f_{I_2}^+)(rs) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s) \end{cases}$
for all $rs \in U_1 \times U_2$,
- (iii) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes t_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes i_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes f_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \end{cases}$
- (iv) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes t_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes i_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes f_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \end{cases}$
for all $r \in U_1, s_1 s_2 \in U_{2j}$,
- (v) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes t_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = t_{I_2}^-(s) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes i_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = i_{I_2}^-(s) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes f_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = f_{I_2}^-(s) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \end{cases}$
- (vi) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes t_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = t_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes i_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = i_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes f_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s)(r_2 s) = f_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \end{cases}$
for all $s \in U_2, r_1 r_2 \in U_{1j}$.
- (vii) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes t_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = t_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes i_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = i_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \boxtimes f_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = f_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \end{cases}$
- (viii) $\begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes t_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = t_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes i_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = i_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \boxtimes I_{2j})}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \boxtimes f_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) = f_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \end{cases}$
for all $r_1 r_2 \in U_{1j}, s_1 s_2 \in U_{2j}$.

Example 3.13. Strong product of IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ shown in Fig. 2 is defined as $\check{G}_{iv1} \boxtimes \check{G}_{iv2} = \{I_1 \boxtimes I_2, I_{11} \boxtimes I_{21}, I_{12} \boxtimes I_{22}\}$ and is represented in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10.

Figure 9: $\check{G}_{iv1} \boxtimes \check{G}_{iv2}$

Figure 10: $\check{G}_{iv1} \boxtimes \check{G}_{iv2}$

Theorem 3.14. Strong product $\check{G}_{iv1} \boxtimes \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \boxtimes I_2, I_{11} \boxtimes I_{21}, I_{12} \boxtimes I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \boxtimes I_{2t})$ of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ of graph structures G_{s1} and G_{s2} , respectively is an IVNGS of $G_{s1} \boxtimes G_{s2}$.

Proof. Consider three cases:

Case 1. For $r \in U_1, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$,

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

for $rs_1, rs_2 \in U_1 \boxtimes U_2$.

Case 2. For $r \in U_2, s_1s_2 \in U_{1j}$,

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(s_1r) \wedge t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(s_2r), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(s_1r) \wedge t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(s_1r) \wedge i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(s_1r) \wedge i_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(s_1r) \wedge f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(s_1r) \wedge f_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

for $s_1r, s_2r \in U_1 \boxtimes U_2$.

Case 3. For $r_1r_2 \in U_{1j}, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-((r_1s_1)(r_2s_2)) &= t_{I_1}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq [t_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [t_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(r_1s_1) \wedge t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^-(r_2s_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+((r_1s_1)(r_2s_2)) &= t_{I_1}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq [t_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [t_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(r_1s_1) \wedge t_{(I_1, \boxtimes I_2)}^+(r_2s_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-((r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2)) &= i_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ &\leq [i_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-(r_2 s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+((r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2)) &= i_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ &\leq [i_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+(r_2 s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-((r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2)) &= f_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ &\leq [f_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [f_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^P(r_1 s_1) \wedge f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^-(r_2 s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+((r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2)) &= f_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1 s_2) \\ &\leq [f_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [f_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1) \wedge f_{(I_1 \boxtimes I_2)}^+(r_2 s_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$r_1 s_1, r_2 s_2 \in U_1 \boxtimes U_2.$$

All cases hold for all $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$. This completes the proof. $\square$

Definition 3.15. Let $\check{G}_{iv1} = (I_1, I_{11}, I_{12}, \dots, I_{1t})$ and $\check{G}_{iv2} = (I_2, I_{21}, I_{22}, \dots, I_{2t})$ be two IVNGSs. Composition of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$, denoted by

$$\check{G}_{iv1} \circ \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \circ I_2, I_{11} \circ I_{21}, I_{12} \circ I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \circ I_{2t}),$$

is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad &\begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs) = (t_{I_1}^- \circ t_{I_2}^-)(rs) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs) = (i_{I_1}^- \circ i_{I_2}^-)(rs) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs) = (f_{I_1}^- \circ f_{I_2}^-)(rs) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s) \end{cases} \\ \text{(ii)} \quad &\begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs) = (t_{I_1}^+ \circ t_{I_2}^+)(rs) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s) \\ i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs) = (i_{I_1}^+ \circ i_{I_2}^+)(rs) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s) \\ f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs) = (f_{I_1}^+ \circ f_{I_2}^+)(rs) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s) \end{cases} \\ &\text{for all } rs \in U_1 \times U_2, \\ \text{(iii)} \quad &\begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (t_{I_1}^- \circ t_{I_2}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (i_{I_1}^- \circ i_{I_2}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \\ f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_1)(rs_2) = (f_{I_1}^- \circ f_{I_2}^-)(rs_1)(rs_2) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1 s_2) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

$$(iv) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ t_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ i_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(rs_1)(rs_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ f_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs_1)(rs_2) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^+(s_1s_2) \end{cases}$$

for all $r \in U_1, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$,

$$(v) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^-(r_1s)(r_2s) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \circ t_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s)(r_2s) = t_{I_2}^-(s) \wedge t_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^-(r_1s)(r_2s) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \circ i_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s)(r_2s) = i_{I_2}^-(s) \wedge i_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^-(r_1s)(r_2s) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \circ f_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s)(r_2s) = f_{I_2}^-(s) \wedge f_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \end{cases}$$

$$(vi) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(r_1s)(r_2s) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ t_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s)(r_2s) = t_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge t_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(r_1s)(r_2s) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ i_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s)(r_2s) = i_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge i_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(r_1s)(r_2s) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ f_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s)(r_2s) = f_{I_2}^+(s) \wedge f_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \end{cases}$$

for all $s \in U_2, r_1r_2 \in U_{1j}$.

$$(vii) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^-(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \circ t_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^-(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \circ i_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^-(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \circ f_{I_{2j}}^-)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2) \end{cases}$$

$$(viii) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ t_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = t_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ i_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = i_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \circ f_{I_{2j}}^+)(r_1s_1)(r_2s_2) = f_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2) \end{cases}$$

for all $r_1r_2 \in U_{1j}, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$ such that $s_1 \neq s_2$.

Example 3.16. Composition of IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ shown in Fig. 2 is defined as $\check{G}_{iv1} \circ \check{G}_{iv2} = \{I_1 \circ I_2, I_{11} \circ I_{21}, I_{12} \circ I_{22}\}$ and is depicted in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12.

Figure 11: $\check{G}_{iv1} \circ \check{G}_{iv2}$

Figure 12: $\check{G}_{iv1} \circ \check{G}_{iv2}$

Theorem 3.17. Composition $\check{G}_{iv1} \circ \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \circ I_2, I_{11} \circ I_{21}, I_{12} \circ I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \circ I_{2t})$ of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ of graph structures G_{s1} and G_{s2} , respectively is an IVNGS of $G_{s1} \circ G_{s2}$.

Proof. Consider three cases:

Case 1. For $r \in U_1, s_1s_2 \in U_{2j}$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= [t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\ &= t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\ &\leq i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= [i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\ &= i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_1) \wedge f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(rs_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+((rs_1)(rs_2)) &= f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs_1) \wedge f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(rs_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$rs_1, rs_2 \in U_1 \circ U_2.$$

Case 2. For $r \in U_2, s_1s_2 \in U_{1j}$

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(s_1r) \wedge t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(s_1r) \wedge t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(s_1r) \wedge i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+((s_1r)(s_2r)) &= i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_1s_2) \\
&\leq i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(s_1r) \wedge i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(s_2r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(s_1 r)(s_2 r) &= f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_1 s_2) \\
&\leq f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(s_2)] \\
&= f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(s_1 r) \wedge f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(s_2 r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(s_1 r)(s_2 r) &= f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_1 s_2) \\
&\leq f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(s_2)] \\
&= f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(s_1 r) \wedge f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(s_2 r),
\end{aligned}$$

$$s_1 r, s_2 r \in U_1 \circ U_2.$$

Case 3. For $r_1 r_2 \in U_{1j}$, $s_1 s_2 \in U_{2j}$ such that $s_1 \neq s_2$

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) &= t_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2) \\
&\leq [t_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [t_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1) \wedge t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_2 s_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) &= t_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2) \\
&\leq [t_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [t_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [t_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [t_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1) \wedge t_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_2 s_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) &= i_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2) \\
&\leq [i_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [i_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_2 s_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) &= i_{I_1}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2) \\
&\leq [i_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [i_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= [i_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [i_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
&= i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1) \wedge i_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_2 s_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2) &= f_{I_1}^-(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2) \\
&\leq [f_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^-(r_2)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^-(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= [f_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^-(r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s_2)] \\
&= f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_1 s_1) \wedge f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^-(r_2 s_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{(I_{1j} \circ I_{2j})}^+((r_1 s_1)(r_2 s_2)) &= f_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1 r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2) \\
 &\leq [f_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_1}^+(r_2)] \wedge [f_{I_2}^+(s_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
 &= [f_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_1)] \wedge [f_{I_1}^+(r_2) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s_2)] \\
 &= f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_1 s_1) \wedge f_{(I_1 \circ I_2)}^+(r_2 s_2),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$r_1 s_1, r_2 s_2 \in U_1 \circ U_2.$$

All cases hold for all $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$. This completes the proof. $\square$

Definition 3.18. Let $\check{G}_{iv1} = (I_1, I_{11}, I_{12}, \dots, I_{1t})$ and $\check{G}_{iv2} = (I_2, I_{21}, I_{22}, \dots, I_{2t})$ be two IVNGSs. Union of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$, denoted by

$$\check{G}_{iv1} \cup \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \cup I_2, I_{11} \cup I_{21}, I_{12} \cup I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \cup I_{2t}),$$

is defined as:

$$(i) \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^-(r) = (t_{I_1}^- \cup t_{I_2}^-)(r) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \vee t_{I_2}^-(r) \\ i_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^-(r) = (i_{I_1}^- \cup i_{I_2}^-)(r) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \vee i_{I_2}^-(r) \\ f_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^-(r) = (f_{I_1}^- \cup f_{I_2}^-)(r) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(r) \end{cases}$$

$$(ii) \begin{cases} t_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(r) = (t_{I_1}^+ \cup t_{I_2}^+)(r) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \vee t_{I_2}^+(r) \\ i_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(r) = (i_{I_1}^+ \cup i_{I_2}^+)(r) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \vee i_{I_2}^+(r) \\ f_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(r) = (f_{I_1}^+ \cup f_{I_2}^+)(r) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(r) \end{cases}$$

for all $r \in U_1 \cup U_2$,

$$(iii) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^-(rs) = (t_{I_{1j}}^- \cup t_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs) = t_{I_{1j}}^-(rs) \vee t_{I_{2j}}^-(rs) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^-(rs) = (i_{I_{1j}}^- \cup i_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs) = i_{I_{1j}}^-(rs) \vee i_{I_{2j}}^-(rs) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^-(rs) = (f_{I_{1j}}^- \cup f_{I_{2j}}^-)(rs) = f_{I_{1j}}^-(rs) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^-(rs) \end{cases}$$

$$(iv) \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^+(rs) = (t_{I_{1j}}^+ \cup t_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs) = t_{I_{1j}}^+(rs) \vee t_{I_{2j}}^+(rs) \\ i_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^+(rs) = (i_{I_{1j}}^+ \cup i_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs) = i_{I_{1j}}^+(rs) \vee i_{I_{2j}}^+(rs) \\ f_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^+(rs) = (f_{I_{1j}}^+ \cup f_{I_{2j}}^+)(rs) = f_{I_{1j}}^+(rs) \wedge f_{I_{2j}}^+(rs) \end{cases}$$

for all $rs \in U_{1j} \cup U_{2j}$.

Example 3.19. Union of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ shown in Fig. 2 is defined as $\check{G}_{iv1} \cup \check{G}_{iv2} = \{I_1 \cup I_2, I_{11} \cup I_{21}, I_{12} \cup I_{22}\}$ and is depicted in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: $\check{G}_{iv1} \cup \check{G}_{iv2}$

Theorem 3.20. Union $\check{G}_{iv1} \cup \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 \cup I_2, I_{11} \cup I_{21}, I_{12} \cup I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} \cup I_{2t})$ of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ of graph structures G_{s1} and G_{s2} is an IVNGS of $G_{s1} \cup G_{s2}$.

Theorem 3.21. If $G_s = (U_1 \cup U_2, U_{11} \cup U_{21}, U_{12} \cup U_{22}, \dots, U_{1t} \cup U_{2t})$ is union of two graph structures $G_{s1} = (U_1, U_{11}, U_{12}, \dots, U_{1t})$ and $G_{s2} = (U_2, U_{21}, U_{22}, \dots, U_{2t})$, then every IVNGS $\check{G}_{iv} = (I, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_t)$ of G_s is union of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ of graph structures G_{s1} and G_{s2} , respectively.

Proof. Firstly, we define I_1, I_2, I_{1j} and I_{2j} for $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} t_{I_1}^-(r) &= t_I^-(r), \quad i_{I_1}^-(r) = i_I^-(r), \quad f_{I_1}^-(r) = f_I^-(r), \\ t_{I_1}^+(r) &= t_I^+(r), \quad i_{I_1}^+(r) = i_I^+(r), \quad f_{I_1}^+(r) = f_I^+(r), \quad \text{if } r \in U_1. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{I_2}^-(r) &= t_I^-(r), \quad i_{I_2}^-(r) = i_I^-(r), \quad f_{I_2}^-(r) = f_I^-(r), \\ t_{I_2}^+(r) &= t_I^+(r), \quad i_{I_2}^+(r) = i_I^+(r), \quad f_{I_2}^+(r) = f_I^+(r), \quad \text{if } r \in U_2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \quad i_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \quad f_{I_{1j}}^-(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \\ t_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad i_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad f_{I_{1j}}^+(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad \text{if } r_1 r_2 \in U_{1j}. \\ t_{I_{2j}}^-(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \quad i_{I_{2j}}^-(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \quad f_{I_{2j}}^-(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \\ t_{I_{2j}}^+(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad i_{I_{2j}}^+(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad f_{I_{2j}}^+(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad \text{if } r_1 r_2 \in U_{2j}. \end{aligned}$$

Then $I = I_1 \cup I_2$ and $I_j = I_{1j} \cup I_{2j}$, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$. Now for $r_1 r_2 \in U_{kj}$,

$$\begin{aligned} t_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) \leq t_I^-(r_1) \wedge t_I^-(r_2) = t_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_k}^-(r_2), \\ i_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) &= i_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) \leq i_I^-(r_1) \wedge i_I^-(r_2) = i_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_k}^-(r_2), \\ f_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) &= f_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) \leq f_I^-(r_1) \wedge f_I^-(r_2) = f_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_k}^-(r_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) \leq t_I^+(r_1) \wedge t_I^+(r_2) = t_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_k}^+(r_2), \\ i_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) &= i_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) \leq i_I^+(r_1) \wedge i_I^+(r_2) = i_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_k}^+(r_2), \\ f_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) &= f_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) \leq f_I^+(r_1) \wedge f_I^+(r_2) = f_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_k}^+(r_2), \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\check{G}_{ivk} = (I_k, I_{k1}, I_{k2}, \dots, I_{kt})$ is an IVNGS of graph structure G_{sk} , $k = 1, 2$. Thus $\check{G}_{iv} = (I, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_t)$ an IVNGS of $G_s = G_{s1} \cup G_{s2}$, is union of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$. $\square$

Definition 3.22. Let $\check{G}_{iv1} = (I_1, I_{11}, I_{12}, \dots, I_{1t})$ and $\check{G}_{iv2} = (I_2, I_{21}, I_{22}, \dots, I_{2t})$ be two IVNGSs and $U_1 \cap U_2 = \emptyset$. Join of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$, denoted by

$$\check{G}_{iv1} + \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 + I_2, I_{11} + I_{21}, I_{12} + I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} + I_{2t}),$$

is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1+I_2)}^-(r) = t_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^-(r) \\ i_{(I_1+I_2)}^-(r) = i_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^-(r) \\ f_{(I_1+I_2)}^-(r) = f_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^-(r) \end{cases} \\ \text{(ii)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(r) = t_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(r) \\ i_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(r) = i_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(r) \\ f_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(r) = f_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(r) \end{cases} \\ & \text{for all } r \in U_1 \cup U_2, \\ \text{(iii)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^-(rs) = t_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^-(rs) \\ i_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^-(rs) = i_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^-(rs) \\ f_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^-(rs) = f_{(I_{1j} \cup I_{2j})}^-(rs) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(iv)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(rs) = t_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(rs) \\ i_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(rs) = i_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(rs) \\ f_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(rs) = f_{(I_1 \cup I_2)}^+(rs) \end{cases} \\
 & \text{for all } rs \in U_{1j} \cup U_{2j}, \\
 \text{(v)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1+I_2)}^-(rs) = (t_{I_1}^- + t_{I_2}^-)(rs) = t_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(s) \\ i_{(I_1+I_2)}^-(rs) = (i_{I_1}^- + i_{I_2}^-)(rs) = i_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(s) \\ f_{(I_1+I_2)}^-(rs) = (f_{I_1}^- + f_{I_2}^-)(rs) = f_{I_1}^-(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(s) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(vi)} \quad & \begin{cases} t_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(rs) = (t_{I_1}^+ + t_{I_2}^+)(rs) = t_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(s) \\ i_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(rs) = (i_{I_1}^+ + i_{I_2}^+)(rs) = i_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(s) \\ f_{(I_1+I_2)}^+(rs) = (f_{I_1}^+ + f_{I_2}^+)(rs) = f_{I_1}^+(r) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(s) \end{cases} \\
 & \text{for all } r \in U_1, s \in U_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.23. Join of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ shown in Fig. 2 is defined as $\check{G}_{iv1} + \check{G}_{iv2} = \{I_1 + I_2, I_{11} + I_{21}, I_{12} + I_{22}\}$ and is depicted in Fig. 14.

Figure 14: $\check{G}_{iv1} + \check{G}_{iv2}$

Theorem 3.24. Join $\check{G}_{iv1} + \check{G}_{iv2} = (I_1 + I_2, I_{11} + I_{21}, I_{12} + I_{22}, \dots, I_{1t} + I_{2t})$ of two IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ of graph structures G_{s1} and G_{s2} , respectively is IVNGS of $G_{s1} + G_{s2}$.

Theorem 3.25. If $G_s = (U_1 + U_2, U_{11} + U_{21}, U_{12} + U_{22}, \dots, U_{1t} + U_{2t})$ is join of two GSs $G_{s1} = (U_1, U_{11}, U_{12}, \dots, U_{1t})$ and $G_{s2} = (U_2, U_{21}, U_{22}, \dots, U_{2t})$, then every strong IVNGS $\check{G}_{iv} = (I, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_t)$ of G_s is join of two strong IVNGSs $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$ of graph structures G_{s1} and G_{s2} , respectively.

Proof. We define I_k and I_{kj} for $k = 1, 2$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, t$ as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{I_k}^-(r) &= t_I^-(r), \quad i_{I_k}^-(r) = i_I^-(r), \quad f_{I_k}^-(r) = f_I^-(r), \\
 t_{I_k}^+(r) &= t_I^+(r), \quad i_{I_k}^+(r) = i_I^+(r), \quad f_{I_k}^+(r) = f_I^+(r), \text{ if } r \in U_k
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \quad i_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2), \quad f_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2), \\
 t_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) &= t_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad i_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2), \quad f_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2), \text{ if } r_1 r_2 \in U_{kj}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now for $r_1 r_2 \in U_{kj}, k = 1, 2, j = 1, 2, \dots, t$
 $t_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) = t_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) = t_I^-(r_1) \wedge t_I^-(r_2) = t_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_k}^-(r_2),$

$$i_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_j}^-(r_2) = i_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_k}^-(r_2),$$

$$f_{I_{kj}}^-(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_j}^-(r_2) = f_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_k}^-(r_2),$$

$$t_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) = t_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) = t_{I_j}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_j}^+(r_2) = t_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_k}^+(r_2),$$

$$i_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_j}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_j}^+(r_2) = i_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_k}^+(r_2),$$

$$f_{I_{kj}}^+(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_j}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_j}^+(r_2) = f_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_k}^+(r_2),$$

Hence $\check{G}_{ivk} = (I_k, I_{k1}, I_{k2}, \dots, I_{kt})$ is a strong IVNGS of graph structure G_{sk} , $k = 1, 2$.

Moreover, we will show that $\check{G}_{iv}$ is join of $\check{G}_{iv1}$ and $\check{G}_{iv2}$. According to the definitions 3.18

and 3.22, $I = I_1 \cup I_2 = I_1 + I_2$ and $I_j = I_{1j} \cup I_{2j} = I_{1j} + I_{2j}$, for all $r_1 r_2 \in U_{1j} \cup U_{2j}$.

When $r_1 r_2 \in U_{1j} + U_{2j}$ ($U_{1j} \cup U_{2j}$), that is, $r_1 \in U_1$ and $r_2 \in U_2$,

$$t_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) = t_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^-(r_2) = t_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge t_{I_k}^-(r_2) = t_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^-(r_1 r_2),$$

$$i_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^-(r_2) = i_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge i_{I_k}^-(r_2) = i_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^-(r_1 r_2),$$

$$f_{I_j}^-(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_1}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^-(r_2) = f_{I_k}^-(r_1) \wedge f_{I_k}^-(r_2) = f_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^-(r_1 r_2),$$

$$t_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) = t_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_2}^+(r_2) = t_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge t_{I_k}^+(r_2) = t_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^+(r_1 r_2),$$

$$i_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) = i_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_2}^+(r_2) = i_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge i_{I_k}^+(r_2) = i_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^+(r_1 r_2),$$

$$f_{I_j}^+(r_1 r_2) = f_{I_1}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_2}^+(r_2) = f_{I_k}^+(r_1) \wedge f_{I_k}^+(r_2) = f_{(I_{1j}+I_{2j})}^+(r_1 r_2).$$

When $r_1 \in U_2, r_2 \in U_1$, we get similar calculations. It's true for $j = 1, 2, \dots, t$.

This completes the proof. $\square$

We have defined the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic line graphs in Definition 2.3. Thus, we close this research article with the following open problems:

Problem 1. Prove or disprove that interval-valued neutrosophic line graph structures are generalization of interval-valued neutrosophic line graphs.

Problem 2. Prove or disprove that if f is a weak isomorphism of interval-valued neutrosophic graph structures onto interval-valued neutrosophic line graph structures, then f is an isomorphism.

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References

- [1] M. Akram, Interval-valued fuzzy line graphs, *Neural Computing & Applications*, 21(2012) 145-150.
- [2] M. Akram and W.A. Dudek, Interval-valued fuzzy graphs, *Computers Math. Appl.*, 61(2011) 289-299.
- [3] M. Akram, N.O. Al-Shehrie and W.A. Dudek, Certain types of interval-valued fuzzy graphs, *Journal of Applied Mathematics*, Volume 2013 Article ID 857070(2013) 11 pages.
- [4] M. Akram, W.A. Dudek and M. Murtaza Yousaf, Self centered interval-valued fuzzy graphs, *Afrika Matematika*, 26(5-6)(2015) 887-898.
- [5] M. Akram and M. Nasir, Concepts of interval-valued neutrosophic graphs, *International Journal of Algebra and Statistics*, 6(1-2)(2017) 22-41 DOI :10.20454/ijas.2017.1235.
- [6] M. Akram and S. Shahzadi, Neutrosophic soft graphs with application, *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 32(1)(2017) 841-858.
- [7] M. Akram, Single-valued neutrosophic planar graphs, *International Journal of Algebra and Statistics*, 5(2)(2016) 157-167.
- [8] M. Akram and G. Shahzadi, Operations on single-valued neutrosophic graphs, *Journal of Uncertain System*, 11(2)(2017) 1-26.
- [9] M. Akram and R. Akmal, Application of bipolar fuzzy sets in graph structures, *Applied Computational Intelligence and Soft Computing*, 2016(2016), Article ID 5859080, 13 pages.
- [10] K. Atanassov, Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Fuzzy sets and Systems*, 20(1986) 87-96.
- [11] P. Bhattacharya, Some remarks on fuzzy graphs, *Pattern Recognition Letter*, 6(1987) 297-302.
- [12] T. Dinesh, A study on graph structures, incidence algebras and their fuzzy analogues[Ph.D.thesis], Kannur University, Kannur, India, (2011).
- [13] T. Dinesh and T.V. Ramakrishnan, On generalised fuzzy graph structures, *Applied Mathematical Sciences*, 5(4)(2011) 173 – 180.
- [14] J. Hongmei and W. Lianhua, Interval-valued fuzzy subsemigroups and subgroups associated by intervalvalued fuzzy graphs, 2009 WRI Global Congress on Intelligent Systems, (2009) 484-487.

- [15] A. Kaufmann, *Introduction a la Theorie des Sous-Ensemble Flous*, Masson et Cie, 1(1973).
- [16] J.N. Mordeson, C.S. Peng, *Operations on fuzzy graphs*, *Information Sci.* 79 (1994) 159-170.
- [17] A. Rosenfeld, *Fuzzy graphs, Fuzzy Sets and Their Applications*, Academic Press, New York, (1975) 77-95.
- [18] E. Sampathkumar, *Generalized graph structures*, *Bulletin of Kerala Mathematics Association*, 3(2)(2006) 65 – 123.
- [19] F. Smarandache, *A unifying field in logics. neutrosophy: neutrosophic probability, set and logic*. Rehoboth:, American Research Press, (1999).
- [20] F. Smarandache, *Neutrosophic set- a generalization of the intuitionistic fuzzy set*, *Granular Computing. 2006 IEEE International Conference*, (2006) 38-42 DOI: 10.1109/GRC.2006.1635754.
- [21] M.S. Sunitha, A. Vijayakumar, *Complement of a fuzzy graph*, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Math.* 33(2002) 1451-1464.
- [22] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y.Q. Zhang and R. Sunderraman, *Single-valued neutrosophic sets*, *Multisspace and Multistruct*, 4(2010) 410-413.
- [23] H. Wang, Y. Zhang and R. Sunderraman, *Truth-value based interval neutrosophic sets*, *Granular Computing, 2005 IEEE International Conference*, 1(2005) 274-277 DOI: 10.1109/GRC.2005.1547284.
- [24] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y.Q. Zhang and R. Sunderram, *An Interval neutrosophic sets and logic: theory and applications in computing*, Hexis Arizona, (2005).
- [25] J. Ye, *Similarity measures between interval neutrosophic sets and their applications in multicriteria decision-making*, *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 26(2014) 165-172.
- [26] L.A. Zadeh, *Fuzzy sets*, *Information Control*, 8(1965) 338-353.
- [27] L.A. Zadeh, *The concept of a linguistic variable and its application to approximate reasoning I*, *Information Sci.*, 8(1975) 199-249.
- [28] L.A. Zadeh, *Similarity relations and fuzzy orderings*, *Information Sciences*, 3(2)(1971) 177 – 200.